

Manuscript # IJPP_620_2024

Original Article (Pharmacology)

**PHARMACOKINETIC MODELLING OF DIGOXIN AND
THEOPHYLLINE: EFFECT OF VOLUME OF DISTRIBUTION
AND PLASMA CONCENTRATION**

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Abstract

This study explores the pharmacokinetic relationship between volume of distribution (V_d), plasma concentration, and maintenance dose for two drugs with narrow therapeutic indices: digoxin and theophylline at constant bioavailability, half-life of elimination, and dosing interval. Using three-dimensional surface plots, the effect of V_d and plasma concentration on the maintenance dose of digoxin and theophylline was analysed. For digoxin, the plot demonstrates that a larger V_d necessitates a higher maintenance dose to achieve therapeutic plasma levels, essential for treating conditions such as heart failure and arrhythmias. Similarly, for theophylline, which is commonly used to manage asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, the interaction between V_d and plasma concentration affects the required maintenance dose. These findings highlight the importance of individualized dosing strategies, considering pharmacokinetic properties of each drug, to ensure efficacy and minimize toxicity. The visualized models offer valuable insights for clinical dosing adjustments based on patient-specific factors such as body composition and organ function,

which can significantly influence the distribution and clearance of these drugs.

Keywords

Pharmacokinetics , Digoxin, Theophylline, Volume of distribution, Plasma concentration

Financial Support and Sponsorship:

Nil

Conflict of Interest

There are no Conflict of Interest

Patient Consent Declaration

Patient's consent not required as there are no patients in this study.

Ethical Approval:

Institutional Review Board approval is not required.

Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Assisted Technology for manuscript preparation

The author(s) confirms that there was no use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Assisted Technology for assisting in the writing or editing of the manuscript and no images were manipulated using the AI.

Manuscript Document Properties:(*Extracted from the manuscript file*)

Word Count	4,053
Character Count	29,684
Approximate Number of Pages (excluding figures)	10

1 **PHARMACOKINETIC MODELLING OF DIGOXIN AND THEOPHYLLINE: EFFECT**
2 **OF VOLUME OF DISTRIBUTION AND PLASMA CONCENTRATION**

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10
11 **ABSTRACT:**

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13 concentration, and maintenance dose for two drugs with narrow therapeutic indices: digoxin and
14 theophylline at constant bioavailability, half-life of elimination, and dosing interval. Using three-
15 dimensional surface plots, the effect of V_d and plasma concentration on the maintenance dose of
16 digoxin and theophylline was analysed. For digoxin, the plot demonstrates that a larger V_d
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23 clinical dosing adjustments based on patient-specific factors such as body composition and organ
24 function, which can significantly influence the distribution and clearance of these drugs.

25 **Keywords:** Pharmacokinetics, Digoxin, Theophylline, Volume of Distribution, Plasma
26 Concentration, Maintenance Dose

27
28 **INTRODUCTION:**

29 Pharmaceutical Technology is a field focused on the development, production, and quality control
30 of pharmaceutical products. This discipline includes formulation science, which involves
31 designing drug products such as tablets, capsules, and injections that ensure stability, efficacy, and

32 patient compliance. It encompasses various processes like compounding, blending, granulation,
33 encapsulation, and coating to transform active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) into safe and
34 effective dosage forms [1-3]. It also plays a critical role in developing controlled-release
35 formulations, which gradually release drugs over time, and targeted delivery systems, which direct
36 drugs to specific areas of the body [4]. Recent advances, such as nanotechnology, biotechnology,
37 and automation, have enabled the development of more sophisticated drug delivery systems that
38 improve bioavailability and therapeutic outcomes. As a whole, pharmaceutical technology bridges
39 scientific discoveries with practical, high-quality products that meet regulatory standards and
40 patient needs [5,6]. Pharmaceutical technology and pharmacology are deeply interconnected [7].
41 While pharmacology focuses on understanding mechanism of action of a drug, therapeutic effects,
42 and interactions within the body, pharmaceutical technology applies this knowledge to design and
43 manufacture formulations that maximize efficacy and safety [8]. Insights from pharmacology
44 about absorption, metabolism, and potential side effects of a drug guide the development of
45 controlled-release or targeted delivery systems, ensuring that the drug reaches its action site at the
46 right concentration and for the appropriate duration. In turn, advances in pharmaceutical
47 technology such as nanoparticle carriers or extended-release formulations enhance
48 pharmacological effects by improving bioavailability, prolonging action, and reducing side effects.
49 Together, these fields ensure that medications are not only effective at a cellular level but are also
50 stable, convenient, and tailored to patient needs, transforming laboratory research into clinical
51 application [9-11].

52
53 Pharmacology is the branch of medicine and biology that examines how drugs interact with living
54 organisms to produce therapeutic or toxic effects. It includes studying drug mechanisms,
55 therapeutic effects, side effects, and interactions within the body [12-13]. Pharmacology is divided
56 into two main areas: pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics. Pharmacodynamics focuses on the
57 biochemical and physiological effects of drugs on the body and how they influence cellular
58 receptors, enzymes, and signal pathways [14]. Pharmacokinetics, a subfield of pharmacology,
59 studies how the body absorbs, distributes, metabolizes, and excretes drugs (often summarized as
60 ADME) [15]. Key pharmacokinetic parameters include the rate of absorption, bioavailability,
61 volume of distribution, and clearance rate. These parameters are crucial for developing effective

62 dosing strategies, minimizing adverse effects, and maximizing therapeutic efficacy of drugs
63 [16,17].

64
65 Digoxin is a cardiac glycoside commonly used to treat heart failure and atrial fibrillation. It
66 strengthens heart contractions by inhibiting the sodium-potassium ATPase enzyme, which
67 increases intracellular calcium in heart muscle cells. It also helps control heart rate in patients with
68 atrial fibrillation by influencing electrical impulse conduction [18-20]. However, digoxin has a
69 narrow therapeutic window, so plasma levels require careful monitoring to avoid toxicity, which
70 can lead to severe side effects like nausea, confusion, and potentially fatal arrhythmias. Its complex
71 pharmacokinetics, influenced by V_d and plasma concentration, affect the maintenance dose
72 required to achieve therapeutic levels while avoiding toxicity [21,22]. Additionally, factors like
73 body weight and renal function contribute to the variability in digoxin distribution among patients
74 [23]. In contrast, theophylline is a bronchodilator primarily used to manage chronic respiratory
75 conditions such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). It works by
76 inhibiting phosphodiesterase, relaxing bronchial smooth muscles and dilating airways, thus
77 improving airflow and relieving breathing difficulties [24]. Theophylline also has mild anti-
78 inflammatory effects, making it beneficial in managing chronic respiratory inflammation. Like
79 digoxin, theophylline has a narrow therapeutic range, and high plasma levels that cause toxicity,
80 with symptoms like nausea, tremors, and seizures. Its pharmacokinetics, including V_d and plasma
81 concentration, play a crucial role in determining effective maintenance doses [25]. Factors like
82 hepatic function and metabolic differences contribute to inter-patient variability in theophylline
83 clearance, presenting challenges in maintaining therapeutic levels without adverse effects [26].

84
85 Digoxin and theophylline require careful management due to their narrow therapeutic windows
86 and variable pharmacokinetic profiles. Although both drugs have been extensively studied in
87 clinical settings, there is limited research on simulation-based studies exploring the combined
88 effects of plasma concentration and V_d on maintenance dose adjustments. Most pharmacokinetic
89 studies rely on real-world patient data, which may overlook the insights provided by simulation-
90 based research in predicting and optimizing dosing regimens. Additionally, the combined impact
91 of V_d and plasma concentration on determining maintenance doses is underexplored in non-clinical
92 modelling contexts. While substantial clinical research has focused on dosing for these

93 medications, simulation-based studies that examine the interaction between plasma concentration,
94 V_d , and maintenance dose adjustments remain scarce. Most existing studies emphasize real-world
95 data and case studies rather than controlled simulations, which could offer valuable insights for
96 dose adjustments. This study addresses this gap by using non-clinical simulation modelling to
97 examine how plasma concentration and V_d influence maintenance dosing for digoxin and
98 theophylline. This approach provides a controlled method for predicting dosing needs that can later
99 be adapted for individualized therapy.

100

101 The primary aim of this study is to simulate the effect of plasma concentration and volume of
102 distribution on the maintenance dosing of digoxin and theophylline, providing insights to guide
103 dosing strategies for these drugs with narrow therapeutic windows. The specific objectives are: (i)
104 To develop a 3-D surface model that quantifies the relationship between plasma concentration,
105 volume of distribution, and maintenance dose for digoxin and theophylline; and (ii) To compare
106 the pharmacokinetic profiles of digoxin and theophylline within the surface plot to identify
107 similarities and differences in their response to varying plasma concentrations and V_d .

108

109 **METHOD:**

110 An online registered version of Matrix Laboratory (MATLAB) from Mathworks, Inc., USA was
111 used for surface plot. Pharmacokinetic data of digoxin and theophylline were collected from an
112 online source [27]. This online resource was initially developed within the framework of a “Swiss
113 virtual Campus” project, in close collaboration with the CENTEF of the University of Lausanne.
114 The content was subsequently transferred to this platform and complemented by the addition of
115 several new pages. This work was coordinated by the eLearning coordinator of the Faculty of
116 Biology and Medicine, University of Lausanne.

117

118 Pharmacokinetic parameters are essential measurements used to understand the fate of a drug
119 within the body, including how it is absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and excreted. These
120 parameters help clinicians determine optimal dosing regimens and predict the concentration of the
121 drug at its target site over time, ensuring therapeutic efficacy while minimizing toxicity [28]. The
122 absorption rate (k_a) refers to how quickly a drug moves from its site of administration (such as the
123 gastrointestinal tract) into the bloodstream. A faster absorption rate leads to a quicker onset of

124 action, while a slower rate may extend the duration of the effects of drug. Bioavailability (F) is the
125 fraction of the administered dose that reaches the systemic circulation in an active form. For orally
126 administered drugs, bioavailability is often less than 100%, due to factors like the first-pass effect
127 in the liver and incomplete absorption. A loading dose (LD) is an initial, often higher, dose of a
128 drug given to rapidly achieve a target plasma concentration, especially for drugs with long half-
129 lives. It helps bring drug levels into the therapeutic range quickly, allowing for faster onset of
130 action.

131

132 Volume of distribution (V_d) indicates the extent to which a drug distributes into body tissues
133 relative to plasma. A high V_d suggests widespread distribution into body tissues, while a low V_d
134 indicates the drug remains primarily in the bloodstream. V_d is crucial for understanding dosing
135 requirements and tissue penetration. Half-life ($t_{1/2}$) is the time required for the plasma concentration
136 of a drug to decrease by half. It reflects how long the drug stays in the body and helps determine
137 dosing frequency. Drugs with shorter half-lives need more frequent dosing, while drugs with
138 longer half-lives require less frequent administration. Clearance (Cl) is a measure of the body's
139 ability to eliminate a drug from the bloodstream, usually through the liver and kidneys. It
140 represents the volume of plasma cleared of the drug per unit time and influences dosing frequency.
141 Drugs with high clearance are eliminated quickly, requiring more frequent doses. The elimination
142 rate constant (k_e) describes the proportion of the drug removed from the body per unit of time. It
143 is closely related to both clearance and half-life, playing a key role in determining how long a drug
144 stays at therapeutic levels. Peak plasma concentration (C_{max}) represents the highest concentration
145 of the drug in the bloodstream after administration. It is important for understanding the intensity
146 of the effects of drug and assessing the risk of toxicity, as higher C_{max} values can increase the
147 likelihood of adverse effects. Time to peak concentration (T_{max}) is the time it takes for the drug to
148 reach its maximum plasma concentration, which is useful for estimating how quickly the drug
149 begins to take effect.

150

151 Area under the curve (AUC) represents the total drug exposure over time, derived from the plasma
152 concentration-time curve. It is used to assess drug absorption, efficacy, and overall exposure.
153 Steady-state concentration (C_{ss}) is the drug concentration in the bloodstream when the rate of drug
154 administration equals the rate of elimination. This concentration is achieved after multiple doses

155 and is important for long-term therapies where a consistent therapeutic effect is needed. The dosing
156 rate is the amount of drug needed per unit time to maintain steady-state plasma levels. The dosing
157 interval (τ) refers to the time between successive doses, which is determined based on the drug's
158 half-life and therapeutic window. A shorter dosing interval helps maintain more stable plasma
159 levels, while a longer interval may allow fluctuations in concentration. Finally, the maintenance
160 dose (MD) is the regular dose needed to keep the plasma concentration within the therapeutic range
161 over time, ensuring that the drug stays at effective levels without causing toxicity. Together, these
162 pharmacokinetic parameters provide critical information for tailoring drug therapy to individual
163 patients. They are especially important for drugs with narrow therapeutic windows, where precise
164 control over plasma levels is necessary to achieve the desired therapeutic effect while avoiding
165 adverse outcomes.

166

167 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**

168 **Effect of plasma concentration and volume of distribution on maintenance dose for digoxin:**

169 Figure 1 represents the relationship between three pharmacokinetic variables: volume of
170 distribution (L) on the x-axis, plasma concentration (ng/mL) on the y-axis, and the loading dose
171 of digoxin (mg) on the z-axis, which is indicated by both the height of the surface and the colour
172 gradient. Analysing this plot help provide insights into dosing strategies for digoxin, a medication
173 commonly used to treat heart failure and arrhythmias.

174

175

176 **Figure 1. Effect of plasma concentration and volume of distribution on maintenance dose**
 177 **for digoxin**

178

179 The V_d , shown on the x-axis, reflects how extensively digoxin distributes throughout the tissues
 180 of body. A higher volume of distribution suggests that digoxin is distributed into various body
 181 tissues rather than remaining solely in the bloodstream. The plot indicates that as the volume of
 182 distribution increases, the required maintenance dose of digoxin also increases. This is expected,
 183 as a larger volume of distribution generally means that the drug disperses into more tissue
 184 compartments, necessitating a higher initial dose to achieve the desired therapeutic concentration
 185 in the plasma. Since digoxin has a narrow therapeutic index, its volume of distribution varies based
 186 on factors like age, weight, kidney function, and overall body composition, which significantly
 187 influence its dosing requirements.

188

189 Plasma concentration, represented on the y-axis, is another critical factor for digoxin dosing. It
 190 refers to the amount of digoxin in the blood and is a key measure in ensuring therapeutic efficacy
 191 while avoiding toxicity. Since digoxin has a narrow therapeutic range, maintaining plasma
 192 concentrations within this range is crucial for both effectiveness and safety. In this plot, as plasma
 193 concentration increases, there is a corresponding increase in the required maintenance dose. This

194 trend suggests that higher plasma concentrations require higher doses, though careful monitoring
195 is essential to avoid concentrations that could lead to toxicity.

196

197 The maintenance dose of digoxin (mg), shown on the z-axis represents the regular dose required
198 to keep the plasma concentration of drug within the therapeutic range over time, maintaining a
199 steady state without toxicity or subtherapeutic levels. The colour gradient on the surface plot
200 ranges from blue (indicating lower doses) to yellow (indicating higher doses), illustrating the
201 combined impact of volume of distribution and plasma concentration on the loading dose. As both
202 the volume of distribution and plasma concentration increase, the maintenance dose of digoxin
203 increases proportionally. This relationship is essential for drugs with a narrow therapeutic index,
204 such as digoxin, to reach therapeutic levels quickly without overshooting into toxic levels [20].

205

206 From a clinical perspective, this plot provides useful insights into tailoring digoxin loading doses
207 based on individual patient characteristics. For example, a patient with a larger volume of
208 distribution due to higher body mass or tissue volume may require a higher maintenance dose to
209 achieve the target plasma concentration. Conversely, patients with a smaller volume of distribution
210 might need a lower maintenance dose to avoid excessive plasma concentrations that could lead to
211 adverse effects. This is particularly important for digoxin because factors such as renal function,
212 age, and body composition can significantly impact both its volume of distribution and plasma
213 clearance [21]. In total, this surface plot helps illustrate the delicate balance required in dosing
214 digoxin, where achieving the right plasma concentration is critical for efficacy and safety.
215 Clinicians are encouraged to consider both the volume of distribution and the target plasma
216 concentration when calculating the loading dose, as well as individual patient factors that may alter
217 these parameters. This approach supports precise, patient-specific dosing strategies that maximize
218 therapeutic benefits while minimizing the risk of toxicity, which is especially valuable for a drug
219 with the therapeutic sensitivity of digoxin.

220

221 **Effect of plasma concentration and volume of distribution on maintenance dose for** 222 **theophylline:**

223 Figure 2 provides a valuable visualization of how theophylline, a bronchodilator often used to treat
224 asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, is distributed within the body based on plasma

225 concentration and the volume of distribution. In pharmacokinetics, understanding these
226 relationships is essential for optimizing drug dosage to achieve therapeutic effectiveness while
227 minimizing side effects.
228

229
230 **Figure 2. Effect of plasma concentration and volume of distribution on maintenance dose**
231 **for theophylline**
232

233 The V_d , represented on the x-axis, is a pharmacokinetic parameter that indicates the extent to which
234 theophylline distributes into body tissues relative to the plasma. A higher volume of distribution
235 generally suggests that more of the drug moves into tissues rather than remaining in the blood.
236 This factor is influenced by various physiological attributes, such as body composition and the
237 affinity of drug for fat or water. In this plot, as the volume of distribution increases, the amount of
238 theophylline in the body also rises, reflecting that larger distribution volumes typically mean a
239 larger reservoir of the drug within the body. This characteristic is critical for drugs like
240 theophylline, as it affects how long and how widely the drug acts within the body.

241
242 Plasma concentration, shown on the y-axis, is another crucial variable in the pharmacokinetic
243 profile of a drug. It indicates the amount of theophylline that is present in the blood at any given
244 time. Higher plasma concentrations are typically associated with higher doses or situations where
245 drug clearance is impaired. In clinical practice, maintaining an optimal plasma concentration is

246 vital since theophylline has a narrow therapeutic window; too low a concentration may be
247 ineffective, while too high could lead to toxicity. In the plot, as plasma concentration increases,
248 there is a corresponding rise in the amount of drug in the body. This relationship highlights the
249 importance of careful dosing and monitoring to keep plasma concentrations within a therapeutic
250 range.

251

252 The amount of theophylline in the body, represented by the colour gradient and height of the
253 surface, combines the effects of plasma concentration and volume of distribution. The clear linear
254 increase in this variable with respect to both plasma concentration and volume of distribution
255 suggests a direct proportional relationship, consistent with the pharmacokinetics. This linear trend
256 shows that any increase in either plasma concentration or volume of distribution leads to a
257 proportional increase in the total amount of theophylline within the body. Clinically, this
258 relationship aids in predicting how much drug will be present in the system based on administered
259 doses and individual patient factors, such as body composition, which influence the volume of
260 distribution.

261

262 From a therapeutic standpoint, this plot is useful for understanding how theophylline behaves
263 within different physiological conditions. For instance, in patients with a larger volume of
264 distribution often seen in individuals with higher body fat or altered body water compartments, the
265 drug may spread out more widely within tissues, potentially requiring adjusted dosing to achieve
266 therapeutic plasma levels [29]. Conversely, in patients with decreased volume of distribution,
267 higher plasma concentrations might be reached with standard doses, increasing the risk of toxicity.
268 Therefore, this plot assists clinicians in adjusting dosage to meet individual patient needs and
269 ensure safety. In summary, this surface plot illustrates the interconnectedness of volume of
270 distribution, plasma concentration, and the overall amount of theophylline in the body. By
271 examining these relationships visually, healthcare professionals could better anticipate drug
272 behaviour in the body and make more informed decisions about dosing regimens. Understanding
273 these dynamics is essential for drugs like theophylline, where precise control over plasma levels
274 is necessary due to the risk of adverse effects associated with even slight deviations from the
275 therapeutic range [30].

276

277 Figures 1 and 2 highlight the critical influence of pharmacokinetic parameters, volume of
278 distribution, plasma concentration, and loading/maintenance dose, on achieving therapeutic
279 success with digoxin and theophylline. Both drugs, due to their narrow therapeutic indices, require
280 precise dose adjustments based on individual factors affecting V_d and plasma levels. For digoxin,
281 calculating the correct maintenance dose is essential to rapidly attain effective plasma levels, while
282 dosing of theophylline is fine-tuned to avoid adverse effects due to its broad tissue distribution.
283 These visualizations underscore the importance of patient-specific dosing strategies, particularly
284 in drugs with narrow therapeutic windows.

285

286 **CONCLUSION:**

287 The pharmacokinetic analysis of digoxin and theophylline underscores the critical role of volume
288 of distribution and plasma concentration in dose optimization for drugs with narrow therapeutic
289 indices. For digoxin, a drug primarily used in heart failure and arrhythmia treatment, higher
290 volumes of distribution necessitate increased loading doses to achieve therapeutic plasma levels
291 without risking toxicity. In theophylline, used in respiratory conditions, a similar relationship
292 dictates maintenance dosing to sustain effective plasma levels. The models emphasize that
293 understanding patient-specific pharmacokinetic parameters such as V_d affected by body
294 composition or renal function is essential for tailoring dosing strategies. This approach enhances
295 therapeutic efficacy while minimizing adverse effects, underscoring the importance of
296 individualized medicine in pharmacotherapy for drugs like digoxin and theophylline.

297

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